

REFLECTION OF EASTERN KITABAAT ART IN OGABI MANUSCRIPTED TRANSLATION

Abstract:

This article discusses the reflection of book art in Ogahi's works. The sequence of chapters in the Ogahi works and the place of the chapters of praise and praise in it are given.

Key words:

Kitabaat, hamd(praise), na't, Ogahi, culture, literature

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During his fruitful creative activity, Ogahi translated about 20 works of art, ethics and history from Persian-Tajik into Uzbek. Among them are the best works of world-famous representatives of Indian, Azerbaijani, Tajik-Persian literature, such as Nizami, Dehlavi, Saadi, Jami. Agahi's skillfully translated works form a part of the history of Uzbek literature, and to ignore it is to ignore the great writer's work, to halve it, or to omit a significant part of the history of literature.

Gulistan, one of Agahi's masterpieces of world culture. This rare work by Saadi Sherozi (1184-1292) has been translated into Uzbek several times. Agahi translated the work in 1862-1863. Even after Agahi, there were people who referred to this famous work.

In 1909, "Gulistan" was translated by Murodkhoja haji Solikhhoja's son and published in lithography in Tashkent. In the preface, the translator, after giving some information about Saadi, the author of the book, praises his work and protects him from unjust attackers: "Most of Sa'di's words are. It is not the work of xirmands to talk nonsense and talk trifles.

Over the years, "Yusuf and Zulaykho" has attracted fans of literature. It has not always been easy to read these works directly. Therefore, there is a need for translation in order for the created works to reach their readers. Many translations are made for this purpose. Among the translations made from the literature of the fraternal peoples, the Ogahi translations are noteworthy.

Each book must have an "etiquette classification" for the individual components of Oriental books and books created during the Islamic period. Strict application of the etiquette of creating a work in the art of book writing ("etiquette classification" or "etiquette definition"). The requirements of the author are as follows:

Whatever the advice, the work begins with the name of Allah, that is, "Bismillahir rahmanir rahimim." However, some thinkers began their work with the press in their native language. Agahi gave the publication in Arabic as "Bismillahir guidance". Below we look at its conversion and analysis:

In the Praise section, praise is given to Allah, the Creator, and His beautiful qualities such as His qualities, kindness, oneness, and compassion are mentioned. The praise part in it is 27 bytes. After the word "Bismillahir Rahmanir Rahim" in it, he asks Allah for strength and will to enter this work, and while the field of literature is a vast field, Ogahi humbly says that he is humbly translating "Yusuf and Zulayho".

It is well-known that the peculiarity of our people is to ask Allah for help in every process, to wish them to go through the difficult path of their own. The poet and skilled translator Ogahi also created a beautifully translated work with a unique approach to the translation of this work. It is preferable to quote the words in the above verses to Arabic words, i.e. tools and instruments- tools and equipment, blessing, classic-best, with the words afroz, which is also the originality of the text.

It can also be seen in the above verses that it is written in obedience to the need to ask Allah for ease by taking a risk and doing His way. The text is unique in that it asks for the creation of a mouthful of wisdom in order to spread the affection in the Agahi language, which is being translated with dhikr in the tongue and gratitude in the heart. Arabic, Persian, and Turkish words can also be found in these verses. In the verse in the parts of praise, one can see changes in some words in almost all of the manuscripts but from a textual point of view.

By the way, the epic "Yusuf and Zulayho" was written by many writers on the basis of episodes of the Qur'an, and Ogahi also preferred to convey this to the people as a literary work, as Jami did. He used to say to Allah, "Do not turn me away from His mercy, even if I am wandering in your way." In the verses in Gal, he is thankful that the weapon he needs is the sweet word of the interpreter — that he has given him the skill of ingenuity.

In the translation of Yusuf and Zulaykho, the introductory parts were written by Ogahi himself, who was able to cite in each sentence that he was writing at the risk of the Creator.

There are elements in the translation process that require a different skill from each translator. It is not the translation of the above verse, but the verses written by him, but in the translation of the epic that Agahi wants to come out as he wishes. If we look at the original manuscript of Yusuf and Zulayho, which was written by Jami in Persian, it begins with an introduction, which consists of 13 bytes.

In the foreword to the poem, he also wrote in the medieval tradition of asking Allah for help when he began to write the work. The next three chapters are parts of praise in which the glorification of Allah and his attributes are mentioned. The second chapter was 28 bytes, the third chapter was the same, and the fourth chapter was 13 bytes.

After the praise, of course, move on to the nat part. Suyuma Ganieva and Kasim Sodiqov's book "History of Writing and the Art of Books" describes Nat as follows: "It praises the Prophet Muhammad (saas). He is described as the last prophet, his miracles, the revelation of the Qur'an to him, and his attainment of ascension.

The first bytes of the naat part are the same as the Jami naat part, but the Jami consists of 27 bytes. Both Persian and Arabic words can be found in the naat part of the translated manuscript, but Turkish words have an advantage. Muhammad s.a.v. He used Arabic adjectives to describe his attributes, and used the adjective 'zymyn in his names above. Our Prophet is mentioned as the most beloved among mankind. Beautiful bytes are inscribed in his honor. In the praise section, Agahi mentions that our Prophet was sacred and beloved. Writing that Allah created this world for our Prophet, he says:

In the Na't section, it is written that Muhammad (saas) was born, that man has been sacred on earth since the time of their arrival, and that he is righteous. Jami also says in the naat part.

In the introductory part, Ogahi introduces his position in the world of translation of this work. In the introduction, the talented poet tells about some peculiarities and signs in the book. In the preface, the wajibu tries to give all the qualities of the body.

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